

Supplementary material S1

Towards the next generation models of the rumen microbiome for enhancing predictive power and guiding sustainable production strategies

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Comparison of Reduction Methods for GEMs

	Approach	Principal Basis	Inputs	Output	Applications
[1]	Top-bottom	Algebra Gaussian elimination	*Internal and external metabolites *Stoichiometric Matrix	*Null space matrix *Stoichiometric matrix full and reduced *Enzyme subsets *EFM *Overall stoichiometries	* <i>Methanococcus jannaschii</i> oxidative Pentose Phosphate pathway
[2]	Top-bottom	MILP Minimize number of active reactions subject to biomass flux target. CPLEX	*Stoichiometric matrix *Target growth rate *Full network	*Minimal reaction set per target	<i>E.coli</i> FBA model
[3]	Top-bottom	Graph Theory with MILP Hierarchical classification of reactions TOMLAB CPLEX	*Structure of metabolic network *Full network	*Subnetwork with minimal reaction set	* <i>E.coli</i> aerobic growth on glucose * <i>E.coli</i> ethanol production from pentose sugar * <i>S.cerevisiae</i>
[4]	Bottom-up	LP Maximize cardinality over a nonnegative flux subspace indexed by a set of reactions	Global metabolic model Core set of reactions (active reactions)	*Consistent subnetwork	*Liver data
[5]	Top-bottom	LP Iteratively eliminating reactions from a network Network pruning and compression	*Protected set of reactions *Protected metabolites	* Consistent small or medium scale model for core metabolism with condensed biomass synthesis	* <i>Synechosystis sp.</i> PCC 6803
[6]	Top-bottom	MILP FVA	*Protected set of reactions *Protected metabolites *Degrees of freedom *Protected functions	* Minimal subnetworks	* <i>Helicobacter pilori</i>
[7]	Bottom-up	Minimize the loss of information combining graph-based search methods and optimization methods LP	*GEM *Metabolic subsystems *Substrates and Media concentration *Available physiological data	*Consistent core models	* <i>E. coli</i> central carbon metabolism * <i>P. putida</i> * <i>S. cerevisiae</i> *Chinese Ovary cell *Human metabolism
[8]	Top-bottom	Matrix Algebra	*GEM *Flux vector	*Reduced network with conservation of flux distribution	* <i>E. coli</i> iAF1 1260

MILP: Mixed Integer Linear Programming

Enzyme subsets [1]. Enzyme subsets are identified as connected reactions carrying the same steady-state flux. This approach assumes that those reactions are activated by the same enzyme. Reduction can be achieved by lumping these reactions while keeping the network capabilities and flexibility. The method is based on the comparison of null vectors by using Gaussian elimination. As the algorithm to calculate the enzyme subsets is the same as the one for Elementary Flux Modes calculation, computation is restricted to networks with moderate size. Furthermore, the degree of reduction is limited to the found enzyme subsets.

Minimal Reaction sets. These methods rely on the identification of the key reactions to be knocked-out in order to achieve the minimum required growth sustaining core metabolic functions. A first recursive approach proposed [2] to minimize the number of reactions while keeping a target function, e.g., biomass at a certain minimum level. The minimal set depends on the target which leads to flux redirection due to successive reaction elimination. Although effective, this method suffers from combinatorial explosion. Graph theory was used to alleviate computational calculation time [3], where reactions are classified as essential, extraneous and indeterminate. Only the indeterminate reactions are then classified by using MILP. Applications have proven that these approaches are limited to minimal reaction sets of less than 600 reactions.

FASTCORE [4]: The algorithm searches for a flux consistent subnetwork of the global network that contains all reactions from a core set and a minimal set of additional reactions. FASTCORE is mainly used for reconstruction where the objective is to find the reactions that provide nonzero fluxes. This means that the core reaction set is augmented until a consistent subnetwork is obtained. The size of the core reaction set limits the reduction. This approach allows gaining in flexibility as reactions are being added considering new pathways. However, if reduction is the main objective a trade-off between number of reactions and represented functions is necessary.

redGEM [7]: It reduces GEM into core models focusing on the central metabolism or a subsystem of interest. Resulting core models capture key properties and preserve consistency in terms of biomass and by-product yields, flux and concentration variability. The core models include all fluxes across the subsystems of interest that are identified through network expansion. This method conveys several steps: choosing subsystem, derivation of a stoichiometric matrix that excludes all cofactor pairs, small metabolites and inorganics. Graph search on the stoichiometric matrix helps to link extracellular subsystems to other subsystems. Finally, redGEM employs lumpGEM to find biomass building blocks through balance lumped reactions. The algorithm is applicable to any compartmentalized or non-compartmentalized GEM.

NetworkReducer [5] reduces a given large-scale metabolic network to a smaller subnetwork keeping desired features of the full network. This algorithm considers the network model and a list of protected metabolites, reactions and functions. It applies a pruning step followed by an optional compression step that allows to obtain the maximal growth rates as in the full model and preserves a protected set of reactions representing the central carbon metabolism. This approach provides a meaningful small or medium scale model representing the core metabolism with a condensed biomass synthesis reaction that is consistent with the full-scale model. Additionally, network compression is applied to collapse some reactions, for example from linear pathways, if the reactions are not protected. Network compression works loss-free, that is none of the feasible phenotypes and functions is lost, however, the resulting network is generally not a proper subnetwork of the full system and a mapping of flux distributions (and reactions) between the compressed and the full network can be cumbersome.

miniNW [6] uses MILP to obtain an exact solution to the reduction problem solved by NetworkReducer. In this case, the inputs are a list of protected metabolites and reactions, the degrees of freedom, as well as protected functions and phenotypes. The minimal number of active reactions are found via FVA. The minimization problem is to minimize the sum of all fluxes. A noteworthy feature of miniNW in comparison to NetworkReducer is its ability to compute all minimal subnetworks [9].

The previous algorithms generate a fully functional core metabolic network that preserves a set of important moieties and capabilities from the full network. However, the selection of a subset of reactions might produce losses of information regarding parallel pathways that can be used to attain the same metabolic goal.

A recent approach called NetRed [8] was presented to analyze flux vectors generated from full networks in a reduced network which holds the same flux distribution of the full network. Differently from others, NetRed is based on matrix algebra taking as inputs the stoichiometric matrix, a flux vector, the numerical flux values and a list of protected metabolites. The algorithm generates a reduced network with its corresponding reduced flux vector which is consistent with the flux vector from the full-scale model. NetRed uses the results of FBA simulation and the stoichiometry of the network to generate a reduced network without information loss. The usage of this method requires that all the reactions are expressed as irreversible reactions. The reduction is performed only with the active reactions. Furthermore, the matrix approach allows to map the solution into the full network. An advantage of the algorithm is the use of several flux vectors which respected constructing a lumped biomass reaction that is unique for all the flux vectors. Additionally, the algorithm can compress parallel reactions into one single reaction which decreases the number of reactions. However, the compression may hamper the visualization and link of the derived reactions with the full-scale network as parallel reaction may come from different metabolic pathways.

All of the previous methods have been implemented in MATLAB mostly in the COBRA tool. However, the development of COBRAPy is encouraging the implementation of those methods into the python programming language which is open source and thus enhances collaboration and promotes open science.

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